

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DELINQUENT BEHAVIOR

Kholmurotova Shohista Mirzaliyeva

Termez University of Economics and Service
Department of Social and Humanitarian Sciences

Lecturer

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14289098>

Abstract: In domestic and foreign literature on the sciences of psychology, pedagogy, sociology, philosophy there is no single approach to the concepts of “deviant behavior” or “delinquent behavior”. You can also find synonyms for the phenomenon of deviant behavior, such as deviant behavior, delinquent, asocial, destructive, addictive, pathological, maladaptive, accentuation behavior.

Key words. Deviant behavior, antisocial behavior, autoaggressive, situational criminals.

Deviant behavior is also of particular importance in the interpretation of representatives of Russian scientific schools, which differ from foreign scientific schools in their approach.

Deviance is often seen as an example of behavior that goes beyond socially acceptable norms and role expectations. Deviance is characterized as a violation of social norms and procedures.

Deviance is a characteristic of behavioral actions that do not correspond to social norms and values established by society.

In a broad sense, the concept of "deviance" includes any deviations from social norms accepted in society.

According to the theory of M.A. Kovalchuk, I.Y. Tarkhanova, deviance is the result of a violation of behavior regulated by social norms.

According to the point of view of S.Y. Borodulina, V.I. Dobrenkov, A.I. Kravchenko, I.A. Nevsky, V.G. Stepanov, S.S. Frolov, deviant behavior is the social behavior of an individual or group that is disproportionate to the norms, laws, and rules formed and established in a given society.

When I.S. Kohn defines the concept of deviant behavior, he evaluates it as a system of behaviors that deviate from generally accepted or observed norms of mental health, law, culture, and behavior.

G.I. Kolesnikova also highlighted the process of socialization in her book “Fundamentals of Psychological Counseling and Psychological Correction” in connection with the social behavior of the individual. I.S. Konesha interpreted

deviant behavior as behavior that deviates from at least one of these social norms.

V.G. Bazhenov, on the other hand, comprehensively covers the mechanisms of personal development, the essence of psychological mechanisms for correcting deviant behavior, and the psychological and pedagogical conditions for corrective and developmental work at school.

According to V.F. Shevchuk, the cause of deviant behavior should be understood as a set of behaviors that do not correspond to formal or informal social norms, border on socio-psychological degradation in the individual, and cause negative psychological effects in the social environment.

Many scholars, when explaining their point of view on the concept of deviant behavior, focus on deviations from the norms of social organization of human behavior and deficiencies in mental self-control. In their studies, Russian scientists present approaches to this problem such as the maladaptive appearance of people who are prone to various situations of an asocial, psychosocial, and pathogenic nature, deviations from existing social norms, deviance, and violation of social norms.

According to L.S. Vygotsky, deviant behavior is not a result of physical or nervous system disorders, but rather a characteristic determined by upbringing and conditions. Parents' lack of trust in their children or improper upbringing lays the foundation for the child's future character traits. Difficulties that arise during the upbringing of a person and their failure to comply with the norms established in society are considered in psychology as deviations, that is, violations. According to L.S. Vygotsky's point of view, deviant behavioral traits formed in a person and their consequences can significantly affect his development as a person.

The term "deviant behavior" refers to the behavior of minors that deviates from the social norms and rules accepted in society and is characterized by non-compliance with these norms and rules and their violation. Deviant behavior is especially characteristic of minors. During this period, the personality of adolescents is formed, their self-understanding, knowledge of the world, etc. are determined. However, the formation and development of a person is a complex process, and the difficulties and deviations inherent in it, internal conflicts, and adaptation to various situations in social life are among the works that need to be studied in sociology.

Based on the theoretical data highlighted above, deviant behavior is a pattern of behavior that is based on the lack of positive emotional relationships between

the infant and the mother in early childhood, the lack of a sense of security and trust. Furthermore, deviant behavior is a set of behaviors that arise as a result of a person's avoidance of responsibility for finding the meaning of their life, their inability to positively express themselves, inadequate life relationships and underdeveloped social feelings, incorrect perceptions and, as a result, the formation of distorted thoughts in thinking, and deviations from accepted norms in society

References:

1. Баженов, В.Г. Психологические механизмы коррекции девиантного поведения школьников / В.Г. Баженов, В.П. Баженова. – Ростов н/Д: Феникс, 2007. – 320 с.
2. Колесникова, Г.И. Основы психопрофилактики и психокоррекции: учеб.пособие для студентов вузов / Г.И. Колесникова. – Ростов н/Д: Феникс, 2005. – 185 с.
3. Майерс Д. Социальная психология: Пер. с англ. - СПб, Питер, 1997. - 688 с.].
4. Сярдин В.И., Каверник Е.А. Практикум по психодиагностике. Методики личностной психодиагностики: Учебное пособие. – Севастопол: Авангард, 2018. – 204 с. Фой 7-8.
5. Фромм Э. Анатомия человеческой деструктивности / Э. Фромм. М.: АСТ: АСТ Москва, 2006. 635 с.

